

P vs NP

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P versus NP is considered as one of the most important open problems in computer science. This consists in knowing the answer of the following question: Is P equal to NP? It is one of the seven Millennium Prize Problems selected by the Clay Mathematics Institute. This question was first mentioned in a letter written by John Nash to the National Security Agency in 1955. A precise statement of the P versus NP problem was introduced independently in 1971 by Stephen Cook and Leonid Levin. Since that date, all efforts to find a proof for this problem have failed. To attack the P versus NP question the concept of NP-completeness has been very useful. If any single NP-complete problem can be solved in polynomial time, then every NP problem has a polynomial time algorithm. MONOTONE 3SAT is a known NP-complete problem. We prove MONOTONE 3SAT is in P. In this way, we demonstrate the P versus NP problem.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Complexity Classes, Completeness, Polynomial Time, 3SAT, Quadratic Residue

1 THEORY

An important complexity class is *NP-complete* [7]. A language $L \subseteq \{0, 1\}^*$ is *NP-complete* if

- $L \in NP$, and
- $L' \leq_p L$ for every $L' \in NP$.

If L is a language such that $L' \leq_p L$ for some $L' \in NP\text{-complete}$, then L is *NP-hard* [5]. Moreover, if $L \in NP$, then $L \in NP\text{-complete}$ [5]. A Boolean formula ϕ is composed of

- (1) Boolean variables: x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n ;
- (2) Boolean connectives: Any Boolean function with one or two inputs and one output, such as \wedge (AND), \vee (OR), \neg (NOT), \Rightarrow (implication), \Leftrightarrow (if and only if);
- (3) and parentheses.

A truth assignment for a Boolean formula ϕ is a set of values for the variables in ϕ . A satisfying truth assignment is a truth assignment that causes ϕ to be evaluated as true. A formula with a satisfying truth assignment is a satisfiable formula. We define a *CNF* Boolean formula using the following terms. A literal in a Boolean formula is an occurrence of a variable or its negation [5]. A Boolean formula is in conjunctive normal form, or *CNF*, if it is expressed as an AND of clauses, each of which is the OR of one or more literals [5]. A Boolean formula is in 3-conjunctive normal form or *3CNF*, if each clause has exactly three distinct literals [5].

For example, the Boolean formula

$$(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2) \wedge (x_3 \vee x_2 \vee x_4) \wedge (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_3 \vee \neg x_4)$$

is in *3CNF*. The first of its three clauses is $(x_1 \vee \neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2)$, which contains the three literals x_1 , $\neg x_1$, and $\neg x_2$. A relevant *NP-complete* language is *3CNF* satisfiability, or *3SAT* [5]. In *3SAT*, it is asked whether a given Boolean formula ϕ in *3CNF* is satisfiable. This problem remains in *NP-complete* even if each clause contains either only negated or un-negated variables (*MONOTONE 3SAT*) [7].

In number theory, an integer q is called a quadratic residue modulo n if it is congruent to a perfect square modulo n [8]; i.e., if there exists an integer x such that:

$$x^2 \equiv q \pmod{n}.$$

Otherwise, q is called a quadratic nonresidue modulo n [8]. When in the context is clear the terminology “quadratic residue” and “quadratic nonresidue”, then it is dropped the adjective

“quadratic” [8]. We use the shorthand notations $q R p$ and $q N p$, to indicated that q is a quadratic residue or nonresidue, respectively. [8].

2 RESULTS

THEOREM 2.1. *MONOTONE 3SAT* $\in P$.

PROOF. Let ϕ be a Boolean formula in 3CNF of n variables with m clauses. Let p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n be the first n odd primes such that they have 2 as a quadratic nonresidue. We assign for each variable in the Boolean formula ϕ a unique of these prime numbers such that the variable x_1 will have the prime p_1 and so on consecutively.

We shall say z satisfies ϕ if the assignment $(z R p_1, z R p_2, \dots, z R p_n)$ satisfies ϕ . This means in a satisfying truth assignment T the variable x_1 is true if $z R p_1$ or x_2 is false when $z N p_2$ and so forth. Now, for each clause c_k in ϕ we construct an expression of nonresidues and residues that make the clause false for a possible candidate z . For example, in the clause $c_k = (x_r \vee x_s \vee x_t)$ for $1 \leq r, s, t \leq n$, then a solution of the simultaneous nonresidues $z N p_r, z N p_s$ and $z N p_t$ guarantee the clause will be false because x_r would be false, x_s would be false and x_t would be false. However, we already know that when $z N p_r, z N p_s$ and $z N p_t$, then $(2 \times z) R p_r, (2 \times z) R p_s$ and $(2 \times z) R p_t$ because 2 is a nonresidue modulo every of these chosen primes and the multiplication of a nonresidue with a nonresidue is a residue [8]. Since p_r, p_s and p_t are primes, then we can assure that $(2 \times z) R (p_r \times p_s \times p_t)$ due to the following property: a number x is a residue modulo y when x is a residue modulo for every prime power dividing y [8].

Therefore, when $(2 \times z) R (p_r \times p_s \times p_t)$, then we guarantee the clause c_k will be evaluated as false. In contraposition, in the clause $c_{k'} = (\neg x_r \vee \neg x_s \vee \neg x_t)$ for $1 \leq r, s, t \leq n$, then a solution of the simultaneous residues $z R p_r, z R p_s$ and $z R p_t$ guarantee the clause will be false because x_r would be true, x_s would be true and x_t would be true. Since p_r, p_s and p_t are primes, then we can assure that $z R (p_r \times p_s \times p_t)$ due to the property mentioned above. Hence, when $z R (p_r \times p_s \times p_t)$, then we guarantee the clause $c_{k'}$ will be evaluated as false. Consequently, if we guarantee that some number z complies with $(2 \times z) N (p_r \times p_s \times p_t)$ or $z N (p_r \times p_s \times p_t)$ for every clause c in ϕ , then z will correspond to a satisfying truth assignment for ϕ .

However, it is enough to search a number z between all the values of $0 \leq z \leq (p_{n-2} \times p_{n-1} \times p_n)^2$ such that z and $2 \times z$ complies with the nonresidues of the triple multiplication of primes from each clause due to the following property: a number x is a nonresidue modulo y when x is a nonresidue modulo for at least one prime power dividing y [8]. Certainly, for every triple of odd primes p_i, p_j and p_k , within the numbers between 0 and $(p_i \times p_j \times p_k)^2$ there are the fully combinations of residues and nonresidues between the primes p_i, p_j and p_k [13]. When we mean combinations, we actually want to express for example a number that is residue from p_i and p_j , but it is nonresidue with p_k and so forth. In this way, $(p_{n-2} \times p_{n-1} \times p_n)^2$ is the upper bound which complies that property in ϕ since p_{n-2}, p_{n-1} and p_n are greatest primes. Thus, *MONOTONE 3SAT* $\in P$. Certainly, we can find the first n odd primes such that they have 2 as a quadratic nonresidue just checking for every odd prime p whether

$$p \equiv 3(\text{mod } 8)$$

or

$$p \equiv 5(\text{mod } 8)$$

as a consequence of the Euler’s criterion [13]. Indeed, there are infinitely many primes of the form $8 \times k + 3$ or $8 \times k + 5$ due to Dirichlet’s theorem on arithmetic progressions [14]. Moreover, the n^{th} odd prime which has 2 as a quadratic nonresidue is polynomially bounded by $n \times \ln n$, because of $\pi(x; 8, 3)$ and $\pi(x; 8, 5)$ are asymptotic to $\frac{Li(x)}{\varphi(8)}$ where φ is the Euler’s totient function and Li is the Eulerian logarithmic integral [14]. Consequently, the search of the number z through the iteration

from 0 to $(p_{n-2} \times p_{n-1} \times p_n)^2$ can be done $O(n^7)$. In addition, we can feasible search these special first primes, because we can make the primality test of a number in polynomial time [2]. \square

THEOREM 2.2. $P = NP$.

PROOF. If any single NP -complete problem can be solved in polynomial time, then $P = NP$ [12]. As a consequence of Theorem 2.1, the answer of the P versus NP problem will be $P = NP$. \square

3 DISCUSSION

Cryptography, for example, relies on certain problems being difficult. A constructive and efficient solution to an NP -complete problem such as 3SAT will break most existing cryptosystems including: Public-key cryptography [10], symmetric ciphers [11] and one-way functions used in cryptographic hashing [6]. These would need to be modified or replaced by information-theoretically secure solutions not inherently based on P - NP equivalence.

There are enormous consequences that will follow from rendering tractable many currently mathematically intractable problems. For instance, many problems in operations research are NP -complete, such as some types of integer programming and the traveling salesman problem [9]. Efficient solutions to these problems have enormous implications for logistics [4]. Many other important problems, such as some problems in protein structure prediction, are also NP -complete, so this will spur considerable advances in biology [3].

Indeed, a proof of $P = NP$ could solve not merely one Millennium Problem but all seven of them [1]. This observation is based on once we fix a formal system such as the first-order logic plus the axioms of ZF set theory, then we can find a demonstration in time polynomial in n when a given statement has a proof with at most n symbols long in that system [1]. This is assuming that the other six Clay conjectures have ZF proofs that are not too large such as it was the Perelman's case [1].

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